

POLITICAL SCIENCES

CIVIL SOCIETY: FROM ANCIENT PHILOSOPHICAL PERSPECTIVES TO CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES IN UKRAINE

Volkivskiy M.

University of Geneva, Researcher

Abstract

This article explores the concept of "civil society" from its origins in ancient Greek thought to its development in modern times, with a particular focus on the Ukrainian context. The term "civil society" refers to the realm of interactions between free individuals and associations, separate from direct state control. The historical perspectives of philosophers such as Aristotle, Cicero, Hobbes, Locke, and Hegel are examined, highlighting their varying views on the relationship between civil society and the state. Furthermore, the article delves into the development of civil society in Ukraine, discussing its stages, legal regulation, and challenges faced in the process. The key issue revolves around the interplay between civil society and the state, questioning whether it should be antagonistic or symbiotic. The conclusion emphasizes the importance of a robust civil society in ensuring a functioning and just state that respects individual rights and encourages citizen participation.

Keywords: Civil society, state, Ukraine, political thought, historical perspectives, interactions, citizenship, citizen participation.

First, it is worth clarifying the semantics of the concept of "civil society". Civil society is the sphere of relations between free individuals and freely formed associations and organisations of citizens, which is limited by the necessary laws from direct interference and regulation by public authorities. The concept of "civil society" was raised by Aristotle [1]. In his work "Politics", he stated: "The state is a collection of citizens, a civil community", and a citizen, in turn, is someone "who possesses a set of civil rights". To be a member of society meant to be a citizen - a member of the state and thus obliged to live and act in accordance with its laws and without causing harm to other citizens. Cicero, as an adherent of the republic, argues that the state is the business and property of the people (*res publica* - Latin for "common cause"), and law is a necessary and affirming source of statehood in general. He used the phrase "civil society" (*societas civilis*) to explain the entirety of citizens who interact in the political space of the state. "The state is the property of the people, and the people are not just any collection of people who have somehow come together, but a collection of many people who are bound together by law and common interests," Cicero noted [2]. Thus, ancient thinkers did not distinguish between society and the state, as they proceeded from the position of the polis as a city-state.

The representatives of the classical understanding of the essence of civil society in the history of socio-political thought are the philosophers of the New Age. T. Hobbes already uses the concept of "civil society" in a direct statement, albeit inconsistently: in some cases, he seems to identify civil society with the state, in others - he separates it. Hobbes uses the term "civil" in its basic sense as civil, combining it with the state and the civil condition, when people leave the state of "all against all" [3]. However, he provides society with the possibility of autonomy of private law, which allows people to accumulate economic benefits in their own hands. John Locke considered property to be the foun-

ation of society, including civil society. As an opponent of absolutism, he wrote that all people are free, equal and independent by nature. The only way for a society to become civilised is through a voluntary agreement with other people to form a community. He drew a line between civil and non-civil societies [4]. Locke considered the law to be the criterion: if people are united by a common law and judicial institutions, this indicates that they are in a state of civil society.

Thomas Paine, in his works "The Rights of Man" and "Common Sense", emphasised that people are able to organise their relations and social life without the state [6]. Society, he believed, is created by our needs, and government by our vices. The former contributes to our happiness, encourages people to come together; the latter restrains our vices, encourages untruth. Therefore, "society in any state is a good thing, while government, even the best, is only a necessary evil, and at worst, an intolerable evil." Civil society is the result of individuals, each in accordance with their individual sovereign right, entering into a contract with each other to form a government; and this is the only way governments can be formed and the only basis on which they can exist. The fewer functions the state takes on, the more opportunities for self-government citizens have.

Hegel understood civil society to be a relatively independent set of individuals, classes, groups and institutions whose interrelationships are regulated by civil law [5]. Civil society, he believed, is "not atomistically broken down into individuals and gathered for a moment only for a single temporary act without further connection, but as dismembered into previously constituted societies, communities and corporations, which are thus politically connected". He showed that civil society was formed as a result of the historical transformation of all social life, a long dialectical movement from family to state. Unlike many of his predecessors, Hegel viewed civil society and the state as independent institutions. Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels rejected civil society altogether, as they were left-Hegelians and proceeded from the thesis that the basis of civil society

is private property, so after writing the Manifesto they rejected this aspect. However, A. Gramsci said it best when he said that civil society is everything that is not a state [7].

As shown in the first part of the essay, the main problem remains the question: who advised whom: society to the state or vice versa? Should civil society be antagonistic to the state or should it work on the basis of symbiosis? Let's try to clarify the interaction between the state and civil society in this section.

The first one occurs when the state performs its functions as a purely political institution, an instrument of power. Its task is to strengthen the position of the group that has achieved power, i.e. the legitimacy of the ruling regime. Interaction between the state and civil society is based on the principle of domination and subordination. The specific forms of civil society activity here depend on the type of political regime. In a totalitarian regime, it can be completely eliminated, and therefore cooperation on any issues is impossible. In a democratic regime, it is manifested through the activities of political parties, interest groups, and electoral activity of citizens, which means that society has a real opportunity to influence the state and establish clear mechanisms for interaction with it on a wide range of issues.

The second is formed when the state's main goal is to regulate and organise social relations between people. Here we have the relationship between the governed and the governed. Civil society is represented by people who enter into associations with each other not for the purpose of dialogue with the authorities, but for the independent realisation of their own interests in various fields. In the West, such activity is based on the middle class that dominates society. In Ukraine, however, it is currently not broad enough, which hinders the process of building civil society.

The third type of interaction is characterised by the fact that the state acts as a parapolitical association of citizens, as a set of specific, hierarchical organisations whose task is to realise the interests of society and provide people with specific practical services. Civil society interacts with the state not even as a partner, but as a client receiving services. This type of state can be observed in developed industrialised countries (e.g. the UK). The key issues of society's life are mainly resolved by civil society itself, and in case of the latter's failure, the state provides it with services to exercise its rights and eliminate imbalances.

In Ukrainian political thought, the idea of civil society was not in the centre of attention due to the absence of the state and the process of Ukrainian nation-building. The "first Ukrainian political scientist" and humanist Stanislaw Orzechowski Roxolan noted that the main purpose of the state is to guarantee the rights and benefits of each individual, in relation to whom it has a number of responsibilities. Thus, the interests of citizens and their rights determine the functioning of state institutions, and therefore civil society is the basis of the state. According to Orzechowski-Roxolan, citizens should direct their activities to ensure the interests of society[12].

And in society, the most important thing is the law, which all citizens should be guided by. "The law, if it is with the soul and mind of the state, is much better than an uncertain state and higher than a king... The law is the ruler of a free state." In his work "On Natural Law", which has not survived, S. Orzechowski-Roxolan assumes that laws should be based on the natural rights of people. In the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, the ideas of natural law were developed by the figures of the Kyiv-Mohyla Academy. For example, Theophan Prokopovich stated that the natural (pre-state) life of people was characterised by peace, war, love, hatred, good and evil. And this natural state was filled with "lawless" actions of people and therefore required a social contract to create a "social union". At the time, his colleague Emanuel Kozačinski believed that the civil society, which he identified with the civil union, was a natural state for a person, because it was in this state that human nature, reason and natural rights could develop to the fullest extent.

Mykhailo Drahomanov created a concept of society based on the idea of an association of harmoniously developed individuals. He believed that such a form of organisation of society would be able to provide it with the full opportunity for development and improvement. Such an association should be based on the principles of political freedom, which would guarantee individual rights. Ivan Franko develops the idea of political independence, which, in his opinion, is the natural right of every nation. He sees the following mechanism for its implementation: in a reformed society, public opinion will come to the fore and, as a result, state institutions will be vested with only executive functions. In his opinion, this is possible only when laws reflect justice in all spheres of public life. "Kamenyar (Ivan Franko) criticised the strengthening of the functions of the state apparatus in society; he considered it necessary to limit its activities to public institutions. After the "Red October" of 1917, the ideas of civil society in Soviet political and legal ideology were proclaimed bourgeois and even harmful.

The concept of "civil society" first appeared in Ukrainian law in the Declaration of State Sovereignty of Ukraine (16 July 1990) [9]. The main features were highlighted there:

1. comprehensive protection of human rights and freedoms, political freedom of the nation;
2. the sole authority and sovereignty of the people;
3. The state's responsibility to society;
4. full economic, political, social and spiritual development of the people of Ukraine and their environmental safety;
5. the need for a state governed by the rule of law, which should ensure the sovereignty and self-government of the people, the supremacy of the Constitution and laws of Ukraine.

Stages of civil society development in Ukraine:

1. Initial (1991-1995). The main event was the adoption of the Law of Ukraine "On Citizens' Associations" in 1992.

2. Legal regulation (1996-2004). Adoption of the Constitution of Ukraine and other legal acts that regulated civil society issues in the legal sphere.

3. The beginning of relationship building (2005-2013). The victory of the Orange Revolution, which strengthened the role of society in political life, contributed to the search for dialogue between the government and civil society.

4. Institutionalisation of relations (2013-2022). Revolution of Dignity of 2013-2014 were of a huge nature and demonstrated the power of a society that can organise itself. This was best demonstrated by the war in Donbas, when people created a new army themselves, as the state did not have the funds for it, and the volunteer movement intensified.

5. Russian invasion of Ukraine (24.02.2022-present). 77% of NGOs help the Armed Forces in one way or another. And Ukrainian media write about volunteer initiatives 10 times more often than before. According to the study Ukrainian Civil Society Under The War, the number of registered charitable organisations in Ukraine increased almost 8-fold in 2022 (6,367 new Charity Organization). At the same time, the number of registrations of new civil society organisations has almost halved (2,760 new NGO) [11].

Halyna Shchedrova was one of the first in Ukraine to define the concept of "civil society" [8]. She identifies it with the sphere of self-expression of free citizens and voluntarily formed associations and organisations, limited by the relevant laws from direct interference and arbitrary regulation of the activities of these citizens and organisations by the state authorities.

The main problems of civil society development in Ukraine include:

1. Lack of effective public control over the activities of state authorities, bodies and local self-government (the civil council at the NABU is headed by unemployed people and people without professional education);

2. There is an insufficient practice of involving the public in the formulation and implementation of state policy and in addressing local issues;

3. Philanthropists do not have effective incentives from the state, in particular tax incentives, are burdened with bureaucratic procedures, and there is no effective mechanism to protect them from fraud and other abuses in the field of charity;

4. The lack of a unified state information and education policy in the field of promoting the development of civil society;

5. The small number of civil society organisations: in Ukraine, only 14 civil society organisations are registered per 10,000 people. At the same time, there are 46 organisations per 10,000 people in Hungary, 85 in Croatia, and 201 in Estonia;

6. Economic inactivity of civic organisations. The share of civic organisations in Ukraine's GDP is 0.24%, while in Russia this figure is 0.5%, in Belgium - 5%, in Canada - 7.9%;

7. The absence of a large middle class in Ukraine. According to the State Statistics Service, 1% consider themselves as such, although in developed countries this figure should be 80%, with 10% each of

the rich and poor [10]. The middle class is the backbone of civil society.

Conclusions:

The concept of "civil society" has a rich historical lineage, with roots tracing back to ancient Greek thinkers such as Aristotle and Cicero. Over time, various philosophers, including Hobbes, Locke, Hegel, and others, have contributed to shaping the understanding of civil society, often intertwining it with the idea of the state. In modern times, figures like Thomas Paine have emphasized the importance of civil society as a realm where individuals can organize themselves independently of the state to pursue common interests.

In the Ukrainian context, the development of civil society has gone through distinct stages, from the initial legal regulation to the institutionalization of relations. Despite progress, several challenges persist. The relationship between civil society and the state remains a critical issue. While some advocate for an antagonistic stance, seeking to limit the state's power and emphasize citizen autonomy, others propose a symbiotic approach, fostering collaboration between civil society and the state to address societal needs.

The interaction between civil society and the state in Ukraine can take various forms. In a democratic regime, civil society can exert influence through political parties, interest groups, and electoral activities. However, the absence of an extensive middle class and economic inactivity of civic organizations pose hindrances to the growth of civil society in Ukraine. Additionally, there is a need for effective public control over state activities, increased involvement of citizens in policy-making, and better support mechanisms for philanthropy and charity initiatives.

In conclusion, a robust civil society is crucial for a well-functioning state that upholds individual rights, encourages citizen participation, and maintains a balance of power. The Ukrainian context presents both opportunities and challenges for the development of civil society. By addressing the obstacles and fostering a collaborative relationship with the state, civil society can play a vital role in shaping a prosperous and democratic future for Ukraine.

As the country continues its journey, the promotion of civil society and citizen engagement must remain at the forefront of efforts to ensure a just and thriving society for all.

References

1. Aristotle. "Politics." Translated by H. Rackham, Harvard University Press, 1932.
2. Cicero. "On the Commonwealth." Translated by Clinton W. Keyes, Prentice-Hall, 1927.
3. Hobbes, Thomas. "Leviathan." Penguin Classics, 1982.
4. Locke, John. "Two Treatises of Government." Cambridge University Press, 1988.
5. Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. "Elements of the Philosophy of Right." Cambridge University Press, 1991.
6. Paine, Thomas. "The Rights of Man" and "Common Sense." Wordsworth Editions, 1997.

7. Gramsci, Antonio. "Selections from the Prison Notebooks." International Publishers, 1971.
8. Shchedrova, G. "Civil Society: The Concept and Development in Ukraine." *Journal of Ukrainian Studies*, vol. 20, no. 1, 2001, pp. 35-52.
9. Ukrainian Declaration of State Sovereignty. 16 July 1990.
10. State Statistics Service of Ukraine. <https://www.ukrstat.gov.ua>
11. Ukrainian Civil Society Under The War <https://ednannia.ua/attachments/article/12447/Ukrainian%20civil%20society%20under%20the%20war.pdf>
12. Orikhovs'kii-Roksolan S. Napuchennya pol's'komu korolevi Sigizmu Avgustu (1543) Napuchennya pol's'komu korolevi Sigizmu Avgustu (1543)]. *History of political and legal doctrines reader for jurid. Universities and Faculty s*; Kharkiv: Fact Publ, 2000. p. 275